

Transformational Principal Leadership on Teacher Performance: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The principal as an educational leader in school institutions has an important role in advancing the educational institutions he leads. The success or failure of educational institutions is strongly influenced by the ability of the principal as a leader to be able to carry out his duties, one of which is helping teachers in improving their performance. The purpose of this study was to determine the role of transformational leadership on teacher performance. This study uses a literature review. The result of this discussion is the role of transformational leadership causes a teacher to work more enthusiastically and focused, so that the teaching and learning process becomes transformative for every teacher.

KEYWORDS: Educational, Leadership, Principal, Transformational Leadership, Teacher Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The principal is the most important person in an educational institution, because the principal is the leader in the school. The principal is a leader as well as a manager in carrying out the school's vision and mission towards the educational goals to be achieved. The principal as a leader has an active role in improving the quality of education. Therefore, the principal must have good leadership skills and great responsibility in the management of education.

Leadership is a social influence process in which the leader seeks voluntary participation from subordinates in an effort to achieve organizational goals. A leader can be defined as a person who delegates or influences others to act so they can carry out certain goals (Swamy, 2014). Principal leadership is the principal's way or effort in influencing, encouraging, guiding, directing and mobilizing teachers, staff, students, parents and other related parties, to work in order to achieve the goals that have been set. Principal leadership is also an ability and readiness of the principal to influence, guide, direct and mobilize school staff so that they can work effectively in order to achieve the educational and teaching goals that have been set (Dikdasmen, 2002). There are several leadership styles that can be implemented by principals in Indonesia when managing a school to be effective and achieve educational goals, namely managerial leadership, transformational leadership, transactional leadership, teaching, and positive (Gaol, 2017).

LITERATURE REVIEW

TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP

Transformational leadership is seen in building an organization, developing a clear vision, distributing leadership and building a school culture which is necessary for the current restructuring efforts in schools (Leithwood, 1998). In implementing leadership transformational, there are ten principles of transformational leadership that must be considered, namely: (1) the leader's vision is clear and communicated to subordinates; (2) Subordinates' awareness of the meaning and importance of their work tasks, (3) Has an orientation towards achieving a shared vision, (4) Pioneering nature of change, (5) Continuous development of self-potential, (6) Occurrence learning process for subordinates, (7) The occurrence of a process of empowerment of the potential of subordinates, (8) The occurrence of a process of developing innovation and creativity, (9) The realization of a culture of cooperation within the organization, and (10) The creation of a conducive organizational work climate through partnerships, multi-communication levels, and respect for ethics and morality (Harbani, 2008). Transformational leadership is associated with several dimensions such as charismatic traits, inspiring power traits, the ability to actively stimulate the intellectuals of subordinates, and individual tolerance (Bass & M, 1990).

There are five important factors related to transformational leadership, include ideal influence, charisma, inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and adapted considerations (Northouse, 2013). With these factors, principals are encouraged to be wiser in acting and dealing with teachers and educational staff in the school environment. Therefore, transformational leaders are leaders who tend to adopt a democratic approach to their leadership style (Giltinane, 2013). As a result, when the principal implements a transformational leadership style well, it will have the potential to involve stakeholders in achieving educational goals (Bush, 2015). For example, when the principal has good transformational leadership, the principal is able to involve teachers, educational staff, and parents of students so that they play an active role in the development of school effectiveness. In the context of Indonesia, this leadership style is very much needed because democratic principles in school management will encourage the emergence of creative ideas and innovations to advance schools from various parties. Furthermore, effective transformational leadership requires trust between leaders and subordinates (Giltinane, 2013). Principals who have a transformational leadership style play a role in encouraging school development (Yang, 2014). Thus, school principals must be able to build trust in teachers and educational staff so that teachers and education staff are also able to develop leadership and responsibilities. In addition, the principal must also share the school's vision and mission with the school community so that this will create a conducive atmosphere for learning.

TEACHER PERFORMANCE

Performance is defined as work performance and work implementation. So the performance of a teacher can be seen from the achievements obtained by a teacher, how a teacher carries out the learning process and evaluates learning outcomes and provides follow-up to the evaluation of learning, and the work obtained by a teacher (Mulyasa M. , 2009). Teacher performance which is expected to boost the quality and relevance of education, in its implementation in the field, depends on many factors that influence it and are interrelated, for example the principal's leadership factor. The principal's leadership determines the quality, without good leadership, the quality improvement process cannot be carried out and realized (Sallis, 2006). The primacy of the principal's leadership influence is not merely in the form of instructions, but rather a motivation or trigger that can inspire teachers and employees, so that their initiative and creativity develop optimally to improve their performance (Yunarsih, 2008).

Regarding teacher performance, certainly can't be separated from the factors that influence it. There are at least ten factors that can improve teacher performance, both internal and external factors (Mulyasa, 2007). The ten factors are (1) the drive to work; (2) responsibility for the task; (3) interest in the task; (4) appreciation for the task; (5) opportunities for growth; (6) attention from the principal; (7) interpersonal relationships with fellow teachers; (8) MGMP and KKG; (9) guided discussion groups and; (10) library services. Based on this opinion, it can be seen that what can affect teacher performance is the leadership and attention of the principal.

Based on the results of research (Effendhi, 2018), it shows that there is a significant positive influence between the principal's transformational leadership on teacher performance. This is supported by a statement from (Asbari, 2020) which states that transformational leadership has a significant positive effect on teacher performance. Transformational leadership is demonstrated by the leader's ability to change teacher awareness, to inspire staff, and to motivate them to achieve high performance voluntarily beyond formal targets and standards without being coerced by leaders (Luthans, 2002). Different results are shown by research of (Iphank, 2017) which states that transformational leadership style has no significant effect on teacher performance. This implies that the increase or decrease in the level of transformational leadership is not able to have much effect on the increase or decrease in teacher performance.

How important the problem of transformational leadership style to the teacher's performance, the researchers are interested in conducting intensive and adequate research in order to obtain information regarding various things that contribute to thinking in order to broaden horizons for the study of educational science in increasing understanding of education management, especially regarding style transformational leadership on teacher performance. In this case, the presumed dominant factor has a relationship with teacher performance, is transformational leadership style.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the relationship of transformational leadership style to teacher performance. Research contributions are expected to be useful for; (1) Educational institutions, presumably can be used as material for consideration and input/source of information in making policies related to the self- development of educators; (2) teachers as an illustration of the importance of developing themselves to the fullest and having a positive attitude towards performance; (3) other research as a reference in conducting other and subsequent studies.

METHODOLOGY

The author uses a study of literature from several journal articles to compile this scientific paper. The articles in this literature study were obtained from searching through google scholar with the keywords transformational leadership, teacher performance. The search found 9 articles, including articles published in 2012-2022 and in full text form. Articles that meet the criteria are then analyzed narratively.

Table 1. Criteria For Inclusion and Exclusion

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Principal Leadership	Paper, Essay, Thesis
Transformational Leadership	Company, Hospital
Teacher Performance	
Last 10 years article	

RESULT

The following presents the results of the literature review that the author has done. The results obtained focus on transformational leadership on teacher performance, both within the scope of schools and universities. The articles obtained are not only from Indonesia, but from various countries with various respondents. The results of the literature review that the author has done will be shown in the table below:

Table 2. Results of Literature Review

Title	Author (s) and Year	Type of Organization	N	Country	Method	Result
Kepemimpinan Transformasional Kepala Sekolah, Kinerja Guru Dan Mutu Sekolah	Intan Silvana Maris, Aan Komariah, Abubakar (2016)	School	327 respondents	Indonesia	descriptive research	The principal has implemented the indicators in the principal's transformational leadership, so that teacher performance and school quality will increase
Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru	Muhamad Taufik B.K (2019)	School	57 teachers	Indonesia	Questionnaire	Principal transformational leadership as measured by four dimensions, namely idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual simulation, individualized consideration are variables that are quite important in improving the performance of teachers.

Pengaruh Komunikasi, Iklim Organisasi dan Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru SMA	Christifora Rahawarin, Suharsimi Arikunto (2015)	School	140 teachers	Indonesia	ex-post facto design	The principal's leadership with a transformational style, where the principal is trusted and accepted by the school community, is firm, able to socialize the school's vision and mission. In addition, the principal is able to motivate teachers, supervise, and care for individual teachers. Thus, teachers will be eager to actualize their competencies so that teacher performance can increase
Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional Kepala Sekolah, Moral Kerja Guru, dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru SDN Di Kota Merauke	Basilius Redan Werang (2014)	School	69 respondents	Indonesia	quantitative research	Good management affects the performance of teachers in schools
Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru	Luthfi Akbar, Nani Imaniyati (2019)	School	52 teachers	Indonesia	planatory Survey	The implications that can be taken in an effort to improve teacher performance are better, it is necessary to increase the transformational leadership style of the principal
Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Guru Sekolah Dasar	Alice Yeni Verawati Wote, Jonherz Stenlly Patalatu (2019)	School	52 teachers	Indonesia	quantitative research	The application of good leadership will make the workplace atmosphere better, so that teacher performance will be better
Transformational Leadership And Job Performance: A Study Of Higher Education	Dr. Jeevan Jyoti, Sonia Bhau (2016)	School	2 Teachers	India	valuative research	Transformational leadership has direct impact on performance through leader member exchange and satisfaction with leader

School leaders and transformational leadership theory: Time to part ways?	Izhak Berkovich (2016)	School	A respondent	Israel	Combines a review of the critique with a discussion of the utility fit of the theory	Educational administration community not to abandon transformational leadership, but to address its shortcomings and look toward future challenges as the community contemplates the promises the theory holds for the field.
Transformational Leadership and Digital Skills in Higher Education Institutes: During the COVID-19 Pandemic	Hera Antonopoulou, Constantinos Halkiopoulos, Olympia Barlou, Grigorios N. Beligiannis (2021)	University	20 respondents	Greece	Quantitative Research	Leadership outcome has a strong positive correlation with transformational leadership and negative correlation with passive to avoid leadership, confirming that higher transformational leadership implies greater efficiency and satisfaction for employees

DISCUSSION

Transformational leadership is a leadership style in which leaders and their subordinates strive to achieve higher levels of morality and motivation. The parameters used to measure this leadership style are by looking at the level of trust, obedience, admiration, loyalty and respect of the followers. This parameter is used on the grounds that followers of transformational followers will look to continue to do better things to achieve organizational goals (Rahmi, 2014).

Stoner, Freeman, and Gilbert (1995) state that transformational leadership is an attitude that must be possessed by leaders in terms of directing their subordinates in terms of improving performance. Complementing Stoner, Freeman, and Gilbert (1995), groups the notion of leadership into two concepts, namely as a process, and the second as an attribute. The leadership process in question is in terms of directing and moving subordinates to organizational goals. According to Kouzes and Posner's theory, transformational leaders are leaders who must be able to set an example for their subordinates, set a role model for their subordinates, can inspire employees, direct their subordinates to a more distant direction, and provide good motivation. strong for employees so that the employee's performance is good, and ready to accept the challenges ahead for leaders, employees and all contents in an organization. So it can be said that transformational leadership can be defined as the ability of leaders to improve the performance of their employees. With the leadership attitude shown by the principal, the performance of the teachers will increase and thus the teachers will always increase work productivity in the school.

Transformational leadership is more focused on change and inspires followers to commit to the shared vision and goals of an organization or work unit, transformational leadership also challenges followers to become innovative problem solvers, and develops followers' leadership capacity through coaching, mentoring, and providing challenges and support. (Bass, B. M., & Riggio, 2006).

Referring to Hempil and coons theory in yukl, (1994) in Nur Zazin (2011), transformational leadership produces leadership behavior in two dimensions, namely consideration and initiating structure. Consideration is the degree to which the leader acts in a friendly, supportive manner, shows concern for his subordinates, and cares for their legitimacy. While initiating structure is the extent to which a leader determines and structures his own role and the role of subordinates towards the achievement of formal group goals or leaders who tend to pay attention to tasks. This shows that transformational leadership factors affect teacher performance. Based on this statement, leadership is transformational and causes a teacher to work more energetically and focused, so that teaching and learning becomes transformative for every teacher. Based on Bass's theory cited by Robin in Sudarwan Danim (2009) there are four characteristics of transformational leadership, namely: 1) Charismatic, 2) Inspirational, 3) Having intellectual stimulation, 4)

Individualized consideration. The explanation above shows several characteristics of transformational leadership that can improve teacher performance in accordance with the desired expectations.

According to House, et al 1996 in Tatty and Dedy (2010) it is explained that transformational leaders are renewal leaders who can help create an environment of pride, loyalty, not fear and intimidation. The reform leader has the following strategic roles: (1) Improving the appearance of human resources and other resources, as well as to improve quality, increase results, and simultaneously to raise the morale of his subordinates, (2) Not only find and record failures from sources, human resources, but to produce the causes of failure, help subordinates to perform better tasks, (3) Create a productive work environment, display innovative leadership, and train subordinates to carry out tasks.

The characteristics of transformational leaders are, always embracing the obstacles or obstacles that exist in the organization; likes to share power with followers; train, advise and provide answers for organizational progress and career development of followers; and trying to take into account the level of needs and willingness of followers to be more responsible (Bass & Avolio; 1990).

Stephen P. Robbins (2003) states that: "Performance is an effort of individuals who direct them to remuneration which they value, based on their potential". The teacher as the bearer of the task and a central role in the learning process is very necessary to provide good performance as the embodiment and implementation of his professional duties. Because the teacher's performance will affect the results obtained by students during learning. Uno, H.B. and Lamatenggo (2012) stated that: Teacher performance is the behavior of a person who produces certain work results after fulfilling a number of requirements.

Armstrong and Baron (in Wibowo, 2007) state that the factors that influence teacher performance are: (1) Personal factor: indicated by the level of skills, competencies possessed, motivation and individual commitment, (2) Leadership factor: determined by quality encouragement, guidance and support by managers and team leaders, (3) Team factor: indicated by the quality of support provided by colleagues, (4) System factor: indicated by the work system and facilities provided by the organization, (5) Contextual/ situational factors: indicated by high levels of pressure and changes in the internal and external environment.

The ability of the principal in translating the vision, mission and goals of the school in carrying out his leadership duties motivates teachers to improve their performance. Teachers become more creative and productive in carrying out their duties and functions to achieve school goals that have been set together. This is in accordance with Burns' opinion which explains that transformational leadership can increase morality and higher motivation in achieving organizational goals. Transformational leadership can increase the commitment, motivation and trust of subordinates thereby placing organizational goals above personal interests. Teachers as a component of education in schools will improve their performance if they are in high spirit and motivation (Sahgal & Pathak, 2007). Transformational (Setiawan & Muhith, 2013) is an effective leadership behavior in improving teacher performance. Transformational leaders have the ability to motivate educational organizational components in 3 ways/mediums, namely 1) encouraging employees to prioritize group interests, 2) encouraging employees to be more aware of the importance of business results, and 3) increasing higher employee needs such as self-esteem and self-actualization. This opinion strengthens the results of the study that there is a positive and significant effect of transformational leadership on teacher performance.

CONCLUSION

Transformational leadership causes a teacher to work more enthusiastically and focused, so that the teaching and learning process becomes transformative for every teacher. Transformational leadership must have four characteristics, namely: 1) Charismatic, 2) Inspirational, 3) Having intellectual stimulation, 4) Individual consideration. In addition, transformational leadership can be defined as the ability of leaders to improve the performance of their employees. With the leadership attitude shown by the principal, the teacher's performance will increase and thus the teacher will always increase work productivity in schools.

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